

ASSESSMENT OF SMART GRID OPERATION UNDER EMERGENCY SITUATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to assess the effect of temporary disconnection of generation and storage units in smart grids. For this purpose, an optimization algorithm for handling the energy dispatch during equipment downtime (suitable for either emergency equipment disconnection or planned maintenance) is developed, the objective of which is to maximize the renewable energy utilization, supporting the ongoing energy transition. The optimization algorithm receives online feedback from the central control system regarding the status of the repairing operation and modifies the energy dispatch accordingly. Furthermore, it calculates the expected results if the emergency was prevented, by using stored measurements or even forecasts of the RES production and load time-series, if required. In this way it assesses the impact of the emergency to the entire smart grid. The algorithm is applied on a smart grid that includes fuel-based local generation, Photovoltaics (PV) and Wind Turbines (WTs), as well as a storage system. An extensive analysis regarding the resulting fuel-based generation requirements and loss of autonomy is performed, taking into account the possible time intervals during which each of the smart grid's power supply units is disconnected, in order to define the boundaries of the impact of such emergencies.

Keywords: Smart grid, Optimization, Emergencies, Assessment

1 INTRODUCTION

Smart grids constitute advanced distribution networks that allow the efficient incorporation of Distributed Energy Resources (DER), such as Renewable Energy Sources (RES), as well as storage units, e.g., Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) [1]. Although research is mostly focused on their daily operation, it is also important to develop a plan for handling emergencies that may frequently interrupt the smart grids' normal operation and assess their potential impact. Emergency situations may be handled in a variety of ways, depending on the nature and early detection of the fault, from temporarily switching the configuration of the smart grid up to changing the objective of the control [2]. In any case, the efficient handling of an occurring emergency requires modifications in the Energy Management System (EMS) [3]. A major emergency that may require vast changes regarding the optimal decisions of the Distribution System Operator (DSO) is the loss of DER or storage. This might happen due to unpredicted weather conditions, such as strong wind that forces the Wind Farms (WF) to disconnect, or due to extreme snow that forces the Photovoltaics (PVs) to disconnect. It might also happen due to a fault that causes a black out in part of the smart grid, possibly excluding storage units or fuel-based generators from the EMS for a few minutes or even hours [4]. Taking the aforementioned cases into account, it is evident that specialized algorithms are required in order to ensure the seamless and efficient operation of the smart grid at all times.

For example, the authors of [2] present an algorithm for handling the loss of one or more generators in a distribution network equipped with fuel-based DER. In the same way, the authors of [4] propose an optimal emergency EMS in smart grids including RES and storage, dedicated to industrial applications. Furthermore, in [5], a control strategy based on the mathematical approach of the Knapsack Problem is presented for the selection of electrical loads when the main power sources are limited or totally absent. The authors of [6] propose a rule-based algorithm for handling emergencies and unplanned islanding events in microgrids with storage and DER. Finally, the authors of [7] develop a standard-based communication model for EMS during emergency considering not only the usual DER but also Electric Vehicles (EVs) as possible supply units.

The purpose of this paper is to present an algorithm for the optimal EMS of smart grids during an emergency, taking into account fuel-based DER, RES and BESS, applicable in a community with mixed (residential and commercial/industrial) load. The optimizer focuses on the maximization of RES harvesting and the autonomy of the smart grid (as opposed to other optimizers which usually focus on cost) thus supporting the ongoing energy transition and the modern EMS trends, and receives feedback from the monitoring system regarding the status of the repairing actions. Furthermore, the algorithm not only proposes the optimal solution but also

assesses the impact of the emergency in terms of: a) requirements in fuel-based resources, i.e., reduction of “green” energy utilization, and b) loss of autonomy, by comparing the results to the expected ones if the emergency was prevented.

2 METHODOLOGY

The flowchart of the proposed algorithm for handling and assessing the impact of emergencies in a smart grid is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the proposed algorithm.

Once the emergency is detected, the faulty part of the smart grid, potentially including DER, BESS, etc., needs to be disconnected. The modified optimal EMS excludes the faulty equipment from the model and uses the current smart grid measurements as input (PV and WF production, load, state of charge of the BESS, etc.). The output of the modified EMS comprises the optimal decisions regarding the charge/discharge of the BESS, the fuel-based production and RES curtailment, if it is required. The output refers to a certain time-step and

needs to be applied directly. Once the time-step changes, the algorithm needs to be updated by the monitoring system regarding the ongoing equipment repair. In case the repair is not finished, the new smart grid measurements need to be used as input in order for the modified EMS to derive the optimal decisions for the new hourly time-step. The loop is repeated for as many time-steps as required until the repair is finished. At that point, the impact of the emergency needs to be assessed. This is performed by using a) stored measurements, e.g., demand, BESS data, etc., or even b) forecasts, e.g., RES production if the disconnected equipment was a RES plant, for each time-step of the emergency. The aforementioned data are used as input in the usual, non-modified EMS and the results are compared to the ones derived from the modified optimal EMS. In the end, the operation can switch back to normal and the emergency algorithm can be deactivated. As regards the optimizer, the objective function (1) aims to maximize the use of the smart grid's RES production and enhance its autonomy as follows: The use of RES production has zero weight and therefore is not mentioned in the objective function, thus being the optimal/first choice out of all energy sources. The second preferable supply units are the smart grid's BESS (one or more, if existing). Their contribution is considered to be environmental friendly as they can be charged only by RES and enhance the autonomy of the smart grid since they are flexible. Therefore, the energy discharged from each BESS, D_b , has the lowest weight, w_1 . The next preferable supply units are the local fuel-based generators, e.g. diesel generators, G_g , the production of which has a higher weight than the BESS, w_2 . The least preferable source is the main grid, the contribution, Img , of which has the highest weight out of all sources, w_3 . Finally, in order to ensure the maximum use of RES production and the maximum possible autonomy, the curtailed energy from the RES, R_n^{curt} , has the highest weight of all, w_4 .

$$\min F = w_1 \sum_b D_b + w_2 \sum_g G_g + w_3 Img + w_4 \sum_n R_n^{curt} \quad (1)$$

The objective function is limited by constraints (2)-(9). Constraints (2)-(6) refer to each BESS, b . In more detail, constraint (2) is the energy balance of each BESS, where S_b is the stored energy, $S_b^{initial}$ is the initial stored energy, C_b is the energy charged to each BESS and η_b is the efficiency. Constraint (3) limits the stored energy of each BESS according to their minimum and maximum boundaries, S_b^{min} and S_b^{max} , respectively. The maximum energy that can be discharged from / charged to each BESS at each time-step is limited by the boundaries D_b^{max} and C_b^{max} , in constraints (4) and (5), where u_b^{dch} , u_b^{ch} are the binary variables that are activated if the BESS is discharged or charged, respectively. Constraint (6) ensures that the BESS cannot be discharged and charged simultaneously. Constraint (7) refers to the RES production of the n -th plant, R_n , which can be either used in the smart grid, R_n^{use} , or curtailed, R_n^{curt} . Constraint (8) limits the contribution of each fuel-based generator, G_g , according to the nominal values, G_g^{max} . Constraint (9) is the energy balance of the smart grid at each time-step, where L_i is the load of the i -th node.

$$S_b = S_b^{initial} + C_b \eta_b - D_b / \eta_b \quad (2)$$

$$S_b^{min} \leq S_b \leq S_b^{max} \quad (3)$$

$$D_b \leq D_b^{max} u_b^{dch} \quad (4)$$

$$C_b \leq C_b^{max} u_b^{ch} \quad (5)$$

$$u_b^{dch} + u_b^{ch} = 1 \quad (6)$$

$$R_n = R_n^{use} + R_n^{curt} \quad (7)$$

$$G_g \leq G_g^{max} \quad (8)$$

$$\sum_i L_i + \sum_b C_b = \sum_b D_b + \sum_g G_g + \sum_n R_n^{use} + Img \quad (9)$$

Of course, when one or more units need to be disconnected, the respective decision variables and constraints are automatically removed from the EMS. This constitutes a Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) problem, and the solver used is Bonmin.

3 CASE STUDY

The proposed algorithm is applied on a hypothetical smart grid located in Athens, Greece, which feeds a community with residential and commercial/industrial load derived from the benchmark systems of [8], including RES [9], one BESS [10] and one diesel generator [11], as presented in Table 1. The BESS is sized according to the average RES exceeding production and the diesel generator is sized according to the fundamental load requirements of the system. The selection of the simulated day (which is the 11th of February) is based on the daily PV production, i.e. 19.2 MWh and the daily WF production, i.e. 27.3 MWh, which are close to the average values, i.e. 17.1 MWh and 27.2 MWh, respectively [9].

Table 1. Description of the simulated smart grid.

Component	Nominal values
PV	Installed power: 4 MWp
WF	Installed power: 3 MWp
BESS	Usable energy: 4.5 MWh, Nominal power: 2.5 MW, round-trip efficiency: 0.95
Generator	Installed power: 0.8 MW
Load	Maximum residential load: 3.4 MW, Maximum commercial/industrial load: 0.9 MW

If no emergencies occurred, the daily operation of the smart grid would be the one presented in Figure 2. Taking into account that the acceptable values of the System Average Interruption Duration Index (SAIDI) and the Customer Average Interruption Index (CAIDI) are equal to 1.5 hours and 1.36 hours, respectively, the emergencies presented in this research are considered to last for 3 hours [12]. The examined cases are the following: a) loss of the diesel generator from 6:00 until 9:00, b) loss of RES from 11:00 until 14:00, and c) loss of the BESS from 16:00 until 19:00. The time intervals are selected according to the worst case scenario in terms of expected contribution of each component.

Figure 2. Daily operation for the simulated day without considering emergencies.

4 RESULTS

The results regarding each emergency case are presented in Figure 3 - Figure 5 and the impact of each emergency is presented in Table 2. It is noted that an emergency affecting the diesel generator when it is utilized the most reduces the autonomy of the smart grid (during the respective 3-hour interval) by 39%, since its production is replaced by energy from the main grid. Furthermore, an emergency affecting the RES when they are at their peak reduces the use of non-fuel-based energy by 95% as the BESS is not charged with enough energy at that time in order to be capable of supplying the load. Therefore, the diesel generator and the main grid cover most of the demand. Yet, since the nominal power of the diesel generator is not high enough to cover the load, the demand is mostly covered by the main grid, thus reducing the autonomy by 68%. Also, since the BESS cannot be charged by the RES (the production of which would have exceeded the demand during the emergency), at the end of the emergency it will have zero usable energy stored, instead of 2.6 MWh, which will affect the operation of the smart grid afterwards. Finally, an emergency affecting the BESS when it is discharged the most reduces the use of environmental friendly energy and the smart grid's autonomy by 43% and 19%, respectively. Overall, the research results indicate that an emergency affecting the RES may

have the worst impact on the smart grid, while the loss of the diesel generator may decrease its autonomy and the loss of the BESS decreases mostly the use of “green” energy.

Figure 3. Results of emergency without diesel generator.

Figure 4. Results of emergency without RES.

Figure 5. Results of emergency without BESS.

Table 2. Impact of emergencies.

Faulty component	Use of non-fuel-based energy (%)			Autonomy (%)		
	Normal	Emergency	Reduction	Normal	Emergency	Reduction
Diesel generator	44%	44%	0%	72%	44%	39%
RES	100%	5%	95%	100%	32%	68%
BESS	100%	57%	43%	100%	81%	19%

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents an algorithm for handling emergencies in smart grids with a rich energy mix and high RES penetration, aiming to assess the potential impact of each main power supply unit's temporary disconnection. The algorithm prioritizes renewable energy over conventional resources, but also the smart grid's autonomy, and is applied on a smart grid including PVs, a WF, one diesel generator and one BESS that can only be charged by RES. The results indicate that the temporary disconnection of each component may affect the smart grid's operation negatively and highlights that an emergency affecting the RES may have the greatest impact on the smart grid, decreasing its environmental friendly operation by 95% and its autonomy by 68%, while also leading to reduced participation of the BESS in the energy mix after the end of the emergency.

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